

Happy New Year

Current status

Thank you to everyone who returned data to us over the last month. Currently, 35% of participants have completed all stages (Table 1) while a significant number of participants remain at earlier stages. We would be grateful if you would let us know by **20 January** an estimated date that you will complete all stages by.

Alpha data. These results are presented in various forms later in this newsletter. Taylor diagrams are displayed, grouped by time-period considered (Figs. 2-49) and plots of the data, ranked by RMSE value and grouped by model classification (Figs. 50-97). Details of the data plotted are provided in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. Figure 1 provides details to assist interpretation of the Taylor Diagrams. The “Results Interpretation Details” section explains the classes and time periods definition.

AMS Annual Meeting, Phoenix, 11 – 15 January 2009

A number of papers will be presented at this conference regarding this Energy Balance Comparison Project. Please, will those of you making relevant presentations at the conference forward us a copy so we can make it available to all participants. These details will be uploaded to the project web pages at: <http://geography.kcl.ac.uk/micromet/ModelComparison/index.htm>

7th International Conference on Urban Climate, Yokohama, 29 June – 3 July 2009

The deadline for submitting abstracts to for this conference has been extended to **24 January 2009**. Please let us know if you have, or plan to, submit papers relevant to this project. See Newsletter 11 for the abstract we have submitted.

Table 1: Current status of each modelling group

- 3.5: Stage 3.5 back?
- 4d: Stage 4 data released?
- 4: Stage 4 output & parameters returned?
- VL92 re-run: ✓/✗ will/will not re-run; - await response.
- MC – model classification ✓confirmed; - await response (see Tables 5-8 in December’s newsletter)
- PM – parameter confirmation (from Newsletter 11)

Parameter survey

In the last newsletter, a list of all parameters for which we have received details, was circulated. It still seems possible that many of these might be reducible to a smaller number (Table 2). Please let us know by **20 January** if you DISAGREE with this. Please also return confirmation of the parameters which were circulated with Newsletter 11, if you have not done so. Further, we want to separate out those parameters which are state variables (Table 3). If your model is indicated, please confirm by **20 January**, whether these values are truly parameter or state variable in relation to your model(s).

Model number	3.5	4d	4	4, Optimised for:	VL92 re-run?	MC	PM
a) Stages 1 – 2 complete							
11				Remains at Stage 2	✗	✓	
12	✓	✓			✗	✓	
13	✓				✗	✓	
14	✓	✓			✗	✓	
16	✓	✓	✓	[Q*], [Q _H], [Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✓	✓	✓
17				Remains at Stage 1.5	-	-	
21	✓	✓			✗	✓	✓
22				Remains at Stage 1.5	-	-	
25	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✗	✓	✓
28				Remains at Stage 2	✗	✓	
30	✓	✓			✗	✓	✓
31		✓	✓	[Q*], [Q _H], [Q _E], [Q _H ,Q _E], [Q*,Q _H]	✓	✓	
32	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✗	✓	✓
33		✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✗	✓	
35	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H]	✓	✓	
36	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H ,Q _E]	✓	✓	✓
37	✓	✓			✗	✓	
39					✓	✓	✓
42	✓	✓	✓	[Q*,Q _H]	✓	✓	
43	✓	✓	✓	[Q*], [Q _H], [Q _E], [Q _H ,Q _E], [Q*,Q _H]	✓	✓	✓
46	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
47					✓	-	✓
49	✓	✓			✗	✓	✓
50		✓			✗	-	
c) Await stages 1 – 2							
26					✓	-	
41					-	-	

Results: Stages 1, 1.5 and 2

The remainder of this newsletter provides a comparison of the results for Stages 1, 1.5 and 2 of this project, See

Table 2: Details of potentially reducible parameters.

Derivable parameter	Derivable from
Vegetation fraction (F_V)	Sum of grass and tree fractions ($F_G + F_T$)
Roughness length for heat (z_{0H})	Roughness length for momentum (z_{0M}) and ratio of surface roughness lengths

Table 3: Details of parameters / state variables.

Parameter (P) / State variable (S) (delete as appropriate)	P / S	To hear from modelling group
Surface temperature	P / S	13,21,37,47,59
Surface temperature of road	P / S	14,16,25,28,31,47
Surface temperature of roof	P / S	16,25,28,31,47
Surface temperature of wall	P / S	16,25,28,31,47
Surface temperature of soil	P / S	13,16,21,31,32,37,47,49
Temperature of root zone	P / S	31
Temperature of deep soil	P / S	16,31,33,35,36,42,47
Internal building temperature	P / S	12,14,16,17,22,25,31,35,36,42,46,47

Table 4: Details of the Taylor diagrams presented.

Stage	Figure #	Fluxes	Classification
1	2-5	Q* ΔQ_S Q_{LE} Q_H	Anthropogenic heat flux
	6-9		Facets and aspects resolved
	10-13		Layers resolved
	14-17		Vegetation inclusion
1.5	18-21		Anthropogenic heat flux
	22-25		Facets and aspects resolved
	26-29		Layers resolved
	30-33		Vegetation inclusion
2	34-37		Anthropogenic heat flux
	38-41		Facets and aspects resolved
	42-45		Layers resolved
	46-49		Vegetation inclusion

Table 5: Details of ranked and grouped RMSE graphs.

Stage	Figure #	Fluxes	Classification
1	50-53	Q* ΔQ_S Q_{LE} Q_H	Anthropogenic heat flux
	54-57		Layers resolved
	58-61		Vegetation inclusion
	62-65		Facets and aspects resolved
1.5	66-69		Anthropogenic heat flux
	67-73		Layers resolved
	74-77		Vegetation inclusion
	78-81		Facets and aspects resolved
2	82-85		Anthropogenic heat flux
	86-89		Layers resolved
	90-93		Vegetation inclusion
	94-97		Facets and aspects resolved

Table 6: Confirmed model classifications (from Newsletter 11).

Vegetation inclusion	
None	11,12,14,17,22,28,33
Separate tile	13,16,21,25,30,31,35,36,37,39,42,45,47,49,50
Integrated	26,32,41,43,46
Layers resolved	
Slab	13,21,30,33,37,41,45,46,49,50
Single	11,22,25,26,28,32,36,39,43,47
Multilayer	12,14,16,17,31,35,42
Facets and aspects resolved (R,W,R - road, wall, roof)	
Whole	33,37,41,49,50
R,W,R with orientation	11,12,14,16,26,28,35,36,42,
R,W,R without orientation	13, 17,21, 22,25,30,31,32,39,43,45,46,47
Anthropogenic heat flux	
None	11, 13,21,28,30,33,37,39,45,46,47,49
Prescribed all	16,17,22,26,32, 36,41,43
Internal	12,14,25,31
Modelled	35, 42,50

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This project contributes to:

MEGAPOLI (EU7)

Funding provided by:

Model Results Interpretation summary

Time Period Definitions

- a) All all data
 - b) Transition: $[Q^*_{t,t+1} < 0 + Q^*_{t+2} \geq 0]$
 $[Q^*_{t,t+1} < 0 + Q^*_{t+2} \leq 0]$
- else
- c) Day $Q^*_t > 0$
 - d) Night $Q^*_t < 0$

These definitions result in varying numbers of data points, as detailed below:

Dataset	Time period	# data points
VL92	All	312
	Day	120
	Night	114
	Transition	78
Alpha	All	8869
	Day	3178
	Night	4549
	Transition	1142

Model Classification Summary

Vegetation inclusion	
None	Assumed to be no vegetation present
Separate tile	Vegetation and built parts of the surface are treated separately Do not interact until a layer above the surface scheme Fluxes are a spatially weighted mean
Integrated	Vegetation is within the tile that has the build facets so can interact/respond to the exchanges associated with this layer of the model

Layers resolved	
Slab	
Single layer	
Multi-layer	

Facets and aspects resolved	
Whole	Individual walls, roof, road are not resolved
Roof, Walls and roads are resolved but <u>without</u> orientation	Sunlit and shaded facets not resolved
Roof, Walls and roads are resolved <u>with</u> orientation	During the daytime there maybe sunlit and shaded facets

Anthropogenic heat-flux	
None	Flux is assumed to be 0 W m^{-2} or not to exist
Prescribed	Flux value is prescribed, considering either: - Some components (partial) - All components
Internal temperature	An internal temperature is prescribed which is used to calculate the other fluxes
Modeled	All or components of the flux are modelled

Figure 1: Taylor Diagram features and how to interpret them. Data are normalised by the standard deviation of the observed data, thereby producing a normalised standard deviation and centred RMSE value of 1.0.

Figure 2: Comparison of Q* for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux method (Alpha Stage 1).

Figure 3: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux method (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 4: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux method (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 5: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux method (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 6: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved consideration (Alpha Stage 1).

Figure 7: Comparison of ΔQ_5 for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved consideration (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 8: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved consideration (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 9: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved consideration (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 10: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1).

Figure 11: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 12: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 13: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 14: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1).

Figure 15: Comparison of ΔQ_S for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 16: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 17: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 18: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 19: Comparison of ΔQ_S for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 20: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 21: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 22: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 23: Comparison of ΔQ_S for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 24: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 25: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 26: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 27: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 28: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 29: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 30: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 31: Comparison of ΔQ_S for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 32: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 33: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 1.5). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 34: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 35: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 36: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 2.

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Figure 37: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 2.

Figure 38: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 39: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 40: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 41: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 6.

Figure 42: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 43: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 44: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 45: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by layers resolved (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 10.

Figure 46: Comparison of Q^* for all models, grouped by vegetation consideration (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 47: Comparison of ΔQ_s for all models, grouped by vegetation method (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 48: Comparison of Q_{LE} for all models, grouped by vegetation method (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 14.

Figure 49: Comparison of Q_H for all models, grouped by vegetation method (Alpha Stage 2). See key in Figure 14.

- Internal
- Not modelled
- Prescribed (all)
- Modelled

Figure 50: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1, all period).

Figure 51: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1, nighttime).

Figure 52: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1, daytime).

Figure 53: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1, transition period).

Figure 54: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1.5, all period).

Figure 55: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1.5, nighttime).

Figure 56: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1.5, daytime).

Figure 57: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 1.5, transition period).

Figure 58: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 2, all period).

Figure 59: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 2, nighttime).

Alpha Stage 2, RMSE, Day data, n = 3178

Figure 60: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_{Hv} , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 2, daytime).

Alpha Stage 2, RMSE, Transition data, n = 1142

Figure 61: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_{Hv} , grouped by anthropogenic heat flux (Stage 2, transition).

Figure 62: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1, all data).

Figure 63: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1, nighttime).

Figure 64: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1, daytime data).

Figure 65: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1, transition data).

Figure 66: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1.5, all data).

Figure 67: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1.5, nighttime data).

Figure 68: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1.5, daytime data).

Figure 69: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 1.5, transition).

Figure 70: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 2, all data).

Figure 71: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 2, nighttime data).

Figure 72: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 2, daytime data).

Figure 73: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by layers resolved (Stage 2, transition data).

Figure 74: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_{Hr} , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1, all data).

Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Night data, n = 4549

Figure 75: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1, nighttime data).

Alpha Stage 1, RMSE, Day data, n = 3178

Figure 76: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1, daytime data).

Figure 77: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1, transition data).

Figure 78: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_S , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1.5, all data).

Figure 79: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1.5, nighttime data).

Figure 80: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1.5, daytime data).

Figure 81: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 1.5, transtion data).

Figure 82: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 2, all data).

Figure 83: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 2, nighttime data).

Figure 84: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 2, daytime data).

Figure 85: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q*, ΔQ_s, Q_{LE}, Q_H, grouped by vegetation inclusion (Stage 2, transition data).

Figure 86: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1, all data).

Figure 87: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1, nighttime data).

Figure 88: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1, daytime data).

Figure 89: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1, transition data).

Figure 90: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1.5, all data).

Figure 91: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{Le} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1.5, nighttime data).

Figure 92: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{Le} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1.5, daytime data).

Figure 93: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 1.5, transition data).

Figure 94: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 2, all data).

Alpha Stage 2, RMSE, Transition data, n = 1142

Figure 95: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 2, nighttime data).

Alpha Stage 2, RMSE, All data, n = 8869

Figure 96: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 2, daytime data).

Figure 97: RMSE for (clockwise from top left): Q^* , ΔQ_s , Q_{LE} , Q_H , grouped by facets and aspects resolved (Stage 2, transition data).